

UNVEILING NDMU'S FEEDER SCHOOLS AS INPUT TOWARDS CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the Notre Dame of Marbel University's feeder schools from 2018-2023 and the feeder schools' categories and areas. The five-year enrolment data from the Office of the Registrar served as the data source. Employing a document review and utilizing descriptive statistics, the study identified top 22 feeder schools. The top 1 feeder school of NDMU is its laboratory school, the NDMU Senior High School Department. It has been its consistent top 1 feeder school in five school years. Its average number of graduates that pursued college at NDMU was 2016. Among the 22 schools, seventeen are from South Cotabato where six are from Koronadal where NDMU is located; four from Sultan Kudarat with Notre Dame of Tacurong College as the top feeder school, and one from Cotabato City which is Notre Dame of Cotabato, also a Marist school. Furthermore as regards the school categories, out of 22 schools, one is a state university which is Sultan Kudarat State University Laboratory High School located in the Province of Sultan Kudarat, one private university (NDMU IBED SHS), six Notre Dame schools, 3 private schools, and 11 public high schools which have represented the 9 municipalities and one city of the Province of South Cotabato. This serves as an input for efficient and effective recruitment activities of the institution which is collaboratively done by the Office of the Quality Assurance, Admissions, Promotions, and Scholarships and the Guidance and Testing Center.

Keywords: *Feeder Schools, Notre Dame of Marbel University, Senior High Schools, Document Review, Recruitment*

INTRODUCTION

The higher education institutions in the Philippines have recruitment teams to invite senior high school students to pursue their college education in their schools. Career guidance orientation, open house, inbound marketing like the use of social media and websites, free campus tour, and free scholarship exams are some of the meaningful activities done to be able to disseminate relevant information that would give opportunities for senior high school students to be part of their academic communities.

Universities and colleges connect with senior high schools to efficiently conduct these activities like the career guidance orientation aimed to guide the students with their career choices, to enlighten them of the importance of career planning, and to introduce courses, scholarships, and other important information.

These senior high schools play a significant role as well. For example, the University of the Philippines Integrated School. It is one of the pioneering integrated schools in the Philippines (UP Integrated School: A. Pioneer in the Philippines, 2023). This article further described the three main functions of UPIS. It serves as a laboratory school, as a service school, and as a feeder school. As a laboratory school, UPIS is the practicum and research site of student teachers from UP College of Education and other colleges and units of UP. As a service school, it has reserved slots for the children of employees. And lastly, as a feeder school, where most of its graduates pursue college in UP.

Moreover, these functions of UPIS are also highlighted by former UP Diliman Chancellor Tan (2016) in his column in the Philippine Daily Inquirer. He stated that UPIS carries the same functions. As a laboratory school, it hones the teaching skills of the UP College of Education students who are supervised by learned teachers; as a service school, it is originally meant for the children of UP faculty and staff; and as a feeder school, with hopes that its graduates would eventually get into UP as college students.

In the Philippines, UP remains as the top university (2024 QS World University Rankings). Although it is the country's national university (Republic Act 9500), it has determined its feeder schools like its UPIS. What about the private universities and colleges? Where do their students come from? Have they identified their feeder schools?

The Notre Dame of Marbel University as an institution that has operated since 1946 offers various courses for the young people of the country. It has programs namely: Business Administration, Education, Liberal Arts, Accountancy, Engineering, Computer Science, Information Technology, Nursing, Medical Technology, and Graduate School programs that are Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges and Universities (PAASCU) accredited. NDMU has three international certifications, to wit: ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System Certification (March 2020-March 2024), ISO 14001:2015 Environmental Management System Certification, and ISO 21001:2018 Educational Organization Management System Certification.

Moreover, it is the school's objective to bring the youth's dreams to realities through quality Marist education. These youth come from the different municipalities, cities, and provinces in the country. Which schools do they come from? This is the main objective of this study. It aimed to identify the feeder schools and their locations and categories for efficient and effective recruitment activities. There has been no study about its feeder schools. Hence, this research has been pushed through by the Office of the Quality Assurance, Admissions, Promotions, and Scholarships as the main office that is in charge of recruitment activities. This research supports the quality management principle of the school which is evidence-based. In decisions to be made by QAPS with regard to recruitment, the data will surely help out.

On Evidence-based Decision Making

One quality management principle of the international standards is evidence-based decision making. This means that the best decisions are based on the gathered information and data. Accordingly, to apply this principle, information and data should be collected relevant to the objective and ensure that these information and data should be analyzed appropriately (7 Quality Management Principles, 2024).

According to Mango (2024), data should not passively reside in spreadsheets or databases, instead utilize the data to drive action. Moreover, it is essential in shaping continuous improvement initiatives.

Decisions and curricula based on the analysis and evaluation of data and information are more likely to produce desired results. Facts, evidence and data analysis lead to greater objectivity and confidence in decision-making (International Standard, 2018).

NDMU, as a Marist Institution, ensures that the ideals, heritage, and charism of St. Marcellin Champagnat remain as an integral part of the university's culture, and decisions are made based on the results of evaluations, feedback, research data, and other factual information (Educational Organization Management System Manual, 2024).

On Continuous Improvement

According to the International Standards, successful organizations truly have ongoing focus on improvement. Improvement is essential to maintain and sustain good performance and practice, address internal and external issues and opportunities.

One of the NDMU's management principles is continuous improvement. NDMU as a Center of Educational Excellence, is committed to employ a comprehensive strategic and operational planning process that engages the entire academic community in seeking the best approaches in improving the university's operation in all areas at all levels (Educational Organization Management System Manual, 2024).

The findings of this study will surely be of help in the planning process of the QAPS.

Research Questions

This study determined the feeder schools of Notre Dame of Marbel University from 2018-2023.

1. What are the feeder schools' categories and areas?
2. What continuous improvement can be proposed towards the efficient and effective promotional activities among senior high schools in Region XII?

Significance of the Study

The data may help in the careful planning of the Office of Quality Assurance, Admissions, Promotions, and Scholarships in the efficient and effective recruitment activities to be conducted in its top schools and other schools. It may increase the students' population.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This is a descriptive study that determined the NDMU's feeder schools and their categories and locations. It also described the continuous improvement towards the efficient and effective promotional activities among senior high schools in Region 12. Using the five-year enrolment data from the Office of the Registrar and utilizing the descriptive statistics such as the frequency, mean, and rank, it has identified these feeder schools.

Source of Data

The five-year enrolment data from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2022-2023 from the Office of the Registrar served as the source of data. The documents just listed down schools with the numbers of enrolled students.

Data Gathering Procedure

A request was made addressed to the College Registrar. The five-year enrolment data from School Year 2018-2019 to School Year 2022-2023 were asked from him. When the documents were sent and printed, document review was done. It used Microsoft Excel. It tallied the population. Then, it got the average number of students for five school years. Then, it was ranked. There were twenty-two schools that served as the feeder schools of NDMU. The feeder schools' categories and locations were also determined afterwards.

Data Analysis

This study utilized descriptive statistics specifically the frequency, mean, and rank. The frequency refers to the exact number of enrollees per semester of every school year (2018-2023). The mean is about the average number of students of each school that were enrolled at NDMU in 2018-2023. The rank was based on the average number of enrolled students per school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. NDMU Feeder Schools from SY 2018-2019 to SY 2022-2023

NDMU FEEDER SCHOOLS FROM 2018-2023														
TOP	FEEDER SCHOOLS	S.Y 2022-2023		S.Y 2021-2022		S.Y 2020-2021		S.Y 2019-2020		S.Y 2018-2019		TOTAL		AVERAGE NUMBER OF STUDENTS
		1st sem	2nd sem	1st Sem	2nd Sem									
1	Notre Dame of Marbel University - IBED	268	264	438	414	513	470	489	462	364	349	2072	1959	2016
2	Koronadal National Comprehensive High Scho	150	138	94	89	95	85	133	136	98	92	570	541	556
3	Notre Dame of Tacurong College	45	43	82	73	51	44	44	40	60	55	282	255	269
4	Libertad National High School	48	44	29	26	33	28	36	34	18	18	164	150	157
5	STI College Koronadal	11	9	15	13	21	21	42	37	17	17	106	97	102
6	Norala National High School	26	20	23	22	21	20	21	20	15	14	106	96	101
7	Banga National High School	22	17	24	23	14	12	17	18	13	10	90	80	85
8	St. Alexius College	16	16	19	18	22	15	16	13	14	12	87	74	80
9	Sto. Niño National High School	15	12	17	17	13	10	16	17	12	12	73	68	70
10	Notre Dame of Esperanza, Inc (SK)	14	17	14	12	19	16	14	12	5	5	86	62	64
11	Tampakan National High School	19	17	19	7	14	12	11	12	7	7	70	55	63
12	Notre Dame Of Surala	24	21	13	14	9	6	11	9	5	5	62	55	59
13	Esperanza National High School (Koronadal)	7	4	17	15	9	8	14	13	12	10	50	50	55
14	Notre Dame of Banga	11	12	20	19	4	3	6	7	10	11	51	52	52
15	Tupi National High School	8	9	11	11	10	5	11	8	14	13	54	46	50
16	Notre Dame of Siena School of Marbel	12	10	13	12	6	5	12	11	9	9	52	47	50
17	Sultan Kudarat State University	14	14	7	6	6	6	9	9	8	8	44	43	44
18	T'boli National High School	12	13	7	7	2	2	13	11	6	6	40	39	40
19	Notre Dame of Cotabato	10	8	7	10	3	2	10	7	4	5	34	32	33
20	Tacurong National High School	11	10	11	9	2	4	3	4	4	3	31	30	31
21	Lake Sebu National High School	10	7	14	5	2	2	4	4	5	3	35	21	28
22	St. Lorenzo School of Polomolok, Inc.	16	12	2	1	4	2	2	3	6	6	30	24	27

The table shows the NDMU feeder schools for five school years. It has listed twenty-two senior high schools. The top 1 feeder school of NDMU is its laboratory school, the NDMU Senior High School Department. It has been its consistent top 1 feeder school in five school years. Its average number of graduates that pursued college at NDMU is 2016. It was followed by Koronadal National Comprehensive High School located in the City of Koronadal, South Cotabato with 556 students. Notre Dame of Tacurong College completes the top 3 with 269 students. NDTC is a Diocesan catholic school in Tacurong City that offers basic education to college. The fourth in rank is Libertad National High School from the Municipality of Surallah, South Cotabato with 157 students. Fifth is STI College Koronadal with 102 students. Sixth is Norala National High School in the Municipality of Norala, South Cotabato. Banga National High School is 7th in rank with 85 students. Following Banga is St. Alexius College in Koronadal City with 80 students. Sto. Nino National High School is 9th in rank with 70 students. Notre Dame of Esperanza, Inc. in Sultan Kudarat is 10th in rank with 64 students. 11th in rank is Tampakan National High School with 63 students. Notre Dame of Surala is ranked 12th with 59 students. 13th in rank is Esperanza National High School in Koronadal city. Notre Dame of Banga is 14th in rank with 52 students. Tupi National High School is 15th in rank with 50

students followed by Notre Dame of Siena School of Marbel in the 16th rank. Sultan Kudarat State University Laboratory School in Sultan Kudarat is 17th in rank with 44 students. Tboli National High School is in the 18th rank with 40 students. Notre Dame of Cotabato is in the 19th rank with 33 students. Tacurong National High School is in the 20th rank with 31 students. Lake Sebu National High School is 21th in rank with 28 students. And, St. Lorenzo School of Polomolok Inc. in the Municipality of Polomolok completes the list with 27 students. Most of the listed schools above are known performing schools in the region which able to produce students with exemplary performance in the different fields.

To name a few, Kayla Marie Sarte was awarded a university medal by the Australian National University as outstanding alumna who took up Master of General and Applied Linguistics in 2019 (Academic Accomplishments, 2019; Australian National University, 2019). After having obtained First Class Honors or Masters Advanced Equivalent. She finished her BSEd major in English in 2011 as Summa Cum Laude at NDMU. In history, she is the only awardee of the Notre Dame Medal, the highest award. She graduated from Notre Dame of Surala as class valedictorian.

Dr. Skezeer John Paz who is an alumnus of Libertad National High School finished his BSEd Math as Summa Cum Laude at NDMU in 2011. In the same year, he took and topped the board licensure examination for professional Teachers. He has been serving the NDMU as a college professor since 2011.

Dr. Miko Michiko Cia finished her Bachelor in Elementary Education as Magna Cum laude at NDMU in 2011. She also topped the BLEPT. She has been a college professor since 2012. She was a class valedictorian of Tampakan National High School.

NDMU-IBED is also a top performing school as evidenced by its PAASCU Level 3 status. Two of its notable alumni are Ens. Krystlenn Ivany Quemado who was the top cadet of the Philippine Military Academy in 2022 Class Bagsik-Diwa among the 214 graduates (Agoot, 2022). Also, Atty. Vince Benedict Abu Barrion, a 16th placer in the 2023 Bar Examinations (Supreme Court of the Philippines, 2023).

Dr. Wilter Friaes is from KNCHS. He graduated Cum Laude in 2009 at NDMU and was one of the Top 10 Outstanding Students of the Philippines (TOSP) and at present, he is the president of Philippine Association of Campus Student Advisers (PACSA). He has been an NDMU administrator who handles student affairs and development since 2011.

Dr. Juvy S. Reyes is from KNCHS, too. She finished her BA Philosophy as magna cum laude. She has been the dean of the NDMU Graduate School and had been the college dean of Arts and Sciences.

Adrian Pete Pregonir is from Banga National High School. He graduated Cum Laude in 2024 at NDMU. He was awarded by the Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino as

Makata ng Taon 2024 for his poem “Sa Muhon ng iyong Kabaong Kalibabaon ang mga Guho ng Kahapon” (Makata ng Taon, 2024).

Herman Albert Sionosa from St. Lorenzo School of Polomolok Inc. is a BA Communication student who won champion in the Global Writing Competition by Marshall Cavendish Education last 2022 in Singapore (Marshall Cavendish Education, 2022).

Table 2. School Categories of NDMU Feeder Schools

Categories of NDMU Feeder Schools				
State University Training Department	Notre Dame Schools	Public High Schools	Private Schools	Private University (IBED)
Sultan Kudarat State University	Notre Dame of Surala	Koronadal National Comprehensive High School	STI College Koronadal	NDMU-IBED
	Notre Dame Siena School of Marbel	Libertad National High School	St. Lorenzo School of Polomolok Inc.	
	Notre Dame of Banga	Norala National High School	St. Alexius College	
	Notre Dame of Cotabato	Banga National High School		
	Notre Dame of Esperanza	Tampakan National High School		
	Notre Dame of Tacurong College	Tboli National High School		
		Tacurong National High School		
		Lake Sebu National High School		
		Esperanza National High School		

		Sto. Niño National High School		
		Tupi National High School		
Total: 1	Total: 6	Total: 11	Total: 3	Total: 1

Table 2 presents the categories of schools. Out of 22 schools, one is a state university which is Sultan Kudarat State University Laboratory High School located in the Province of Sultan Kudarat, one private university (NDMU SHS), six Notre Dame Schools, 3 private schools, and 11 public high schools which have represented the 9 municipalities and 1 city of the Province of South Cotabato. The Top 3 feeder schools of NDMU have different school categories namely: Private University, Public High School and a Notre Dame School which is run by a Diocese of Cotabato. These schools offer three or more strands in the SHS such as Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). In total, there are 12 public high schools and 10 private schools.

Table 3. Areas of NDMU Feeder Schools

Province of South Cotabato (17)	Province of Sultan Kudarat (4)	Cotabato City (1)	Total Number of Schools
Koronadal City (6) Surallah (2) Noralala (1) Banga (2) Tampakan (1) Tboli (1) Lake Sebu (1) Tupi (1) Polomolok (1) Sto. Niño (1)	Tacurong (3) Esperanza (1)	Cotabato City (1)	22

Table 3 describes the areas or locations of these feeder schools. Among the 22 schools, seventeen are from South Cotabato which six are from Koronadal where NDMU is located; four from Sultan Kudarat with Notre Dame of Tacurong College as the top feeder school, and one from Cotabato City which is Notre Dame of Cotabato, also a Marist school. In SOCCSKSARGEN, there are two areas, South Cotabato and Sultan

Kudarat. There is none from the Province of Cotabato, Province of Sarangani, and General Santos City given the presence of other schools in Cotabato namely: University of Southern Mindanao which is a top 1 school in Region 12, Notre Dame of Midsayap College, the first Notre Dame School in Asia, and Notre Dame of Kidapawan College, a Marist school. There is no feeder school from the Province of Sarangani given its geographical location and its accessibility to General Santos City which has a number of universities namely: Mindanao State University, Notre Dame of Dadiangas University, a Marist school, and other colleges. At present General Santos City has opened its door to a premiere institution in the country, the University of Sto. Tomas.

Another area of NDMU feeder school is located in Cotabato City which is part of BARMM. Cotabato also has best schools like Notre Dame University which is run by the Oblates of Mary Immaculate Fathers, Cotabato State University, and other colleges, still there are some who opted to enroll at NDMU to continue the Marist quality education. There has been an average number of 33 students from Notre Dame of Cotabato who enrolled at NDMU. Formerly Cotabato City is part of the SOCCSKSARGEN region.

Figure 1. Feeder Schools in SOCCSKSARGEN Region

Continuous Improvement of the Promotional Activities of NDMU among Senior High Schools in Region XII

The Office of Quality Assurance, Admissions, Promotions, and Scholarships may continue to partner with the Guidance and Testing Center for the career guidance orientation activities to be conducted among the senior high schools in Region XII. The feeder schools should be given priority.

Since the top feeder schools are determined, the following are necessary for continuous improvement of the promotional activities:

Identify top graduates of the University who were alumni of these feeder schools. May introduce them through a Powerpoint Presentation or flyers or pamphlet to further encourage and inspire students from their Alma Mater to consider NDMU for their college degrees.

Identify who among the NDMU employees were graduates of these feeder schools. Invite them to join in the career guidance orientation of their Alma Mater. In this way, the students may have models to look up to.

Identify the Alma Mater of the Marist Ambassadors. Encourage them to participate in the promotional activities to be conducted in their Alma Mater.

Identify who among the Entrance Academic and Academic scholars came from these feeder schools. May include them as well in the Powerpoint Presentation to be used in the career guidance activity.

Identify the NDMU topnotchers who were alumni of these feeder schools. May include them as well in the presentation.

Constant communication and collaboration among these feeder schools should be strengthened. May schedule career guidance orientation among these schools ahead of time.

Figure 2. Sample NDMU Pamphlet for KNCHS

Conclusions

The Notre Dame of Marbel University has a good network with public and private senior high schools. However, it needs to focus on strengthening the partnership or linkage with Province of Cotabato, Province of Sarangani, and General Santos City schools.

Recommendation

Intensify the promotional activities of the University and maintain good connection with the feeder schools.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A letter was sent to the Registrar for the five-year data. This was utilized for the purpose of this research only and for the continuous improvement of the services of the Office of Quality Assurance, Admissions, Promotions, and Scholarships.

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